

THE BENEFITS OF DEVELOPMENT-LED ARCHAEOLOGY

Prepared by the 'Making the case for development-led archaeology' Working Group

DEVELOPMENT-LED ARCHAEOLOGY

Archaeology is the study of human activity through the discovery, examination and analysis of material culture. Archaeology offers a unique perspective on human evolution, cultural development, and history. It helps us understand how we became who we are today. Each investigation contributes a small part of this understanding, allowing us to see patterns and chart our human journey.

But development-led archaeology does much more than this and brings substantial additional public benefits. This document summarises those benefits.

Development-led archaeology - also known as preventive, salvage or rescue archaeology - is the process of investigating and recording irreplaceable heritage before it is removed by development. It now makes a very significant contribution to our growing understanding of our past.

With principles enshrined in the [Valletta Convention](#) and under individual state policies and law, archaeologists, paid for either by the developer or the state, explore archaeological heritage being impacted by development, create a record of it, recover artefacts and interpret and publish the results.

This mitigation process should be supported by ensuring that archaeology remains relevant, understood and valued by all those involved in any project – decision-makers, developers, archaeologists and the general public. Handled intelligently, with all the benefits explained well and acknowledged, development-led archaeology is potentially a very positive force that can contribute immeasurably to communities by providing a powerful and visceral sense of place and identity. Fully integrated into the planning of new development investment, archaeological mitigation inspires development design, builds community support and meets corporate social responsibility ambitions.

When properly planned and integrated, with costs and timeframes proportionate to impact, development-led archaeological costs are not a burden. A survey carried out by the European Archaeological Council indicates that across all development projects across Europe, the overall annual investment of development-led archaeology is **less than 1 euro for every 1100 euros spent on construction costs** involving land-development.¹

¹Survey in 2020. Costs for individual developments vary of course, but the majority range mainly between 0.5 and 2% of total development cost, with the great majority of developments not requiring any archaeological input at all.

While the overall cost is relatively minor, it is incumbent on us all to justify it. The strategic benefits arising from that investment need to be understood and championed by decision-makers. These benefits need to be communicated clearly by archaeologists and delivered effectively within the practical constraints of each project. Developers and their backers must, of course, see a positive return from their investment in archaeological works, and at the same time those benefits must have a positive impact on the public.

The European Archaeological Council, an organisation of state archaeologists responsible for archaeological heritage management on behalf of their respective Governments, have assessed the benefits accruing from development-led archaeology. A series of tangible, practical benefits are summarised in the following pages.

While not every development and archaeological project will be able to produce all of these benefits, with the right policies in place, careful planning and a thoughtful approach will achieve greater dividends for all.

THE BENEFITS OF DEVELOPMENT-LED ARCHAEOLOGY

EVIDENCE OF OUR SHARED HISTORY

Development-led archaeology can shape our understanding of the past and our shared history.

Archaeological endeavours have long shaped our understanding of the past and they continue to do so. Recognition of this lies at the heart of successful heritage legislation, international treaties and charters. Shared understanding of where and how society has developed over millennia is a unifying force for all citizens of our world. Development-led archaeological discoveries now drive the vast majority of this new understanding.

STORIES OF DISCOVERY

Archaeological discoveries create major news stories reaching large numbers of citizens.

New discoveries often create much excitement with archaeology engaging people in emotive and genuine ways. Archaeology is a tangible presence of past personal, family or community memories encouraging people to discuss and share their stories and their histories. Development-led archaeological narratives about discoveries can forge a link between the developer and the community, to the benefit of both.

ECONOMIC GROWTH

Development-led archaeology directly contributes economic benefits to investors and communities.

Archaeological discovery inspires a sense of place and can inspire civic design. Where new and old meet constructively in such partnerships, they create places of distinctive richness and value, appreciated by many. This in turn may encourage business and enterprise investment, and drive heritage tourism, providing opportunities for communities and further sustainable investment.

NATIONAL CULTURAL TREASURES

Development-led archaeology discovers and secures outstanding artistic or cultural treasures for permanent display to the public.

Tourism statistics demonstrate the value placed by so many on our landscapes, archaeological monuments, and outstanding artistic and cultural treasures. The compendium of national treasures grows each time through discovery. Through public engagement and interaction, these growing collections are a gift to the future from the past. Development-led archaeology makes an enormous contribution to national stories.

SOURCES OF COMMUNITY PRIDE

Development-led archaeology enhances communities.

Community identity can be bolstered by investment and co-creation centred around discoveries, monuments, and settings. Such heritage-inspired places, often grounded in ancient place names, are sources of significant pride within communities. Development-led archaeology can be a genuine positive force for enhancing community identity.

REFLECTIVE COMMUNITIES

Development-led archaeology contributes to communal reflection and understanding.

Archaeology provides a setting for reflection and understanding and learning. Ancient places of worship, sites of ancient conflict, shipwrecks, and other places of historical note, offer people physical touchpoints to consider and reflect upon matters of belief, spirit, identity and memory.

LIFELONG LEARNING

Development-led archaeology contributes directly to education at all stages of life.

Archaeology contributes directly to life-long education. Whether through town hall presentations, evening lectures, interaction with school children, a museum visit or a guided tour around a neighbourhood, archaeological heritage prompts questions of what, how, why, when and who, inspiring curiosity and galvanising learning, up-skilling and volunteering. It is a vast library of human expression and ingenuity. Developments can create novel and exciting learning opportunities both during and after the investigations.

SCIENTIFIC INNOVATION

Development-led archaeology contributes directly to wider science and innovation in other disciplines and fields of study.

Archaeological remains provide rich resources for the advancement of scientific disciplines through interdisciplinary research. They are of very significant research value in the study of ancient DNA, molecular evidence, evidence for former species and the understanding of evolution, evidence for the incidence, cause and treatment of diseases and the spread of pathogens, biodiversity, the influence of seismic/tectonic stress, and the understanding of climate change. Such ancient discoveries can also drive technological innovation. Development-led archaeology can further enable strategic partnerships which offer much potential in a wide variety of disciplines.

HEALTH AND WELLBEING

Development-led archaeology can improve people's physical and mental wellbeing.

Archaeology can have a wide range of beneficial impacts on the physical, mental and social wellbeing of individuals and communities. Evidence shows the positive impacts of archaeology on individual wellbeing, including outcomes such as increased confidence, social connectivity and life satisfaction. Development-led archaeology has the potential to offer significant benefits here through community participation and place-making.

SOWING THE SEEDS

The key steps required to realise the benefits of development-led archaeology are set out below. Decision-makers may wish to consider how state operations of archaeological investigation could be modified to create the necessary conditions:

- **Early Stakeholder Engagement.** Early and continued engagement between developers, archaeologists, decision-makers and communities ensures potential benefits are identified as early as possible and robust creative measures agreed to ensure their maximum impact.
- **Flexibility.** Some potential benefits may arise from unexpected discoveries during the project development and archaeological works. Flexibility within agreed parameters will enable the realisation of those benefits.
- **Expert Networks.** Investigations and discoveries may raise scientific, ethical, cultural and media issues. Having such expertise in these fields at hand to address such requirements as they arise is important.
- **Evaluation.** Good cooperation between stakeholders will be the most realistic means of realising benefits. An agreed evaluation framework will allow sampling of impact over time.

FURTHER INFORMATION

There is a growing body of case studies which provide real-world examples of the benefits set out above. These can be found in EAC Guidelines 5 [The Benefits of Development-led Archaeology in Europe and Beyond](#)

The European Archaeological Council welcomes communication from all European state heritage bodies and would be happy to answer any further queries.

www.europae-archaeologiae-consilium.org

Working Group Contributors:

Barney SLOANE (Chair)
Ann DEGRAEVE
Kurt FARRUGIA
Desislava GRADINAROVA
Eszter KREITER
Anu LILLAK
Jonas VAN LOOVEREN
Michael MACDONAGH
Adrian OLIVIER
Jon SELIGMAN
Lyudmil VAGALINSKI
Marjolein VERSCHUUR
Sadie WATSON
Annemarie WILLEMS.

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p/a Urban.brussels
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1000 Bruxelles, BELGIUM
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